

The Representation of COVID-19 and China in the Headlines of Reuters and Xinhua

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: December 28 ,2023</p> <p>Accepted: March 29,2024</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Headlines, Critical discourse analysis, Coronavirus, Media agencies, Xinhua, Reuters, China</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10909101</p>	<p><i>The appallingly abominable scare caused by China's sudden hit by the Coronavirus turned out to be insurmountable. Infections and virus contractions have been spreading so swiftly both in China and abroad, calling the World Health Organization (WHO) to declare global health emergency requiring a well-coordinated international stance. By analyzing a corpus of 16,980 English headlines of Reuters and Xinhua from January 8, 2020, to February 29, 2020, the present study seeks to examine the most frequently discussed topics in the headlines in this context. It also investigates how China is represented in the headlines of the two news agencies. Informed by a critical discourse analysis perspective, the headlines are analyzed quantitatively and qualitatively. The representation of the virus in the news headlines of the two agencies reflected some differences in thematic focus. Reuters focused on the immediate and long-term repercussions, serious implications and consequences emerging from the current health crisis. Xinhua's reporting, on the other hand, tended to play down the effect of the coronavirus spread on the Chinese economy and to highlight the readiness and ability of china to overcome and curb the spread of the disease. China is described neutrally most of the time in Reuters, and positively in Xinhua. The study concludes that local media's reporting geared towards enforcing the 'Us vs. 'Them' dichotomy by highlighting the efforts of the government in fighting and curbing the epidemic so vehemently and forcefully.</i></p>

Introduction

Coronaviruses are known to cause respiratory tract illnesses with some common flu symptoms starting with fever, cough, and shortness of breath. The current SARS-like 2019-nCoV, (novel Coronavirus) outbreak originating in Wuhan, mainland China and spreading so fast at a global level raises the question, why China again? According to Richburg (2020), the fact that all three respiratory system infections "bird flu", "SARS" and "2019-nCoV" have originated in mainland China in a relatively short period would suggest that the protective measures taken have not been stringent enough to curb further outbreaks of the same virus. This particular dimension is of paramount importance since a global spread of the virus will transform the outbreak into an uncontrollable pandemic.

Given the intricate nature and mystery surrounding this condition, researching the very nature of the China Coronavirus outbreak is quite complicated and diversified, with its medical, health, economic, social, political, psychological effects, repercussions and consequences. In other words, its impact will reach out to affect different domains and disciplines. As such, the most adequate research methodology hinges on a macro-analysis approach of multidisciplinary nature. Consequently, the analytical approach for this piece of research will be informed and guided by the multi-modal and multi-disciplinary nature of critical discourse analysis (CDA). This study covers the first phase of the COVID-19 outbreak (from January 8, 2020 to February 29, 2020), and depicts the representation of COVID-19 in two major news outlets through analyzing a corpus of 16,980 English headlines of Reuters and Xinhua.

The present piece of research attempts to provide an answer to the following questions:

- 1) What are the most frequently discussed topics in the context of coronavirus in the headlines of the two major news agencies, Reuters and Xinhua (New China Agency)?
- 2) How is China represented in the headlines of the above-mentioned news agencies?

Contextual Background (COVID-19 from January 8, 2020 to February 29, 2020)

The sudden and stealthy outbreak of the China Coronavirus in late 2019 was so stunning and confusing, especially with the death toll and virus infections dramatically rising around the clock. The World Health Organization (WHO) responded so quickly by declaring a state of global emergency. WHO's reaction is indicative of its concern over the gravity of the situation. This health threat, which is reaching the levels of a pandemic, is exploding to reach almost every district in China, and some other parts of the outer world (Secon, Woodward, & Mosher, 2020). On January 3, 44 suspected patients with a mystery disease are reported by China, and a first death due to the new coronavirus is reported on January 9. A spike in cases of COVID-19 was reported on January 18-19. Wuhan closes the airport and railway stations on January 23rd. By January 25, more countries have been affected by COVID-19. WHO Director declared the 2019-nCoV outbreak a public health emergency of international concern on January 30th. 14380 cases of COVID-19 were confirmed in China with the death toll rises above 300 on February 1. The death toll due to COVID-19 reached over 800 on February 9, and 2000 on February 19. The virus affected 44 countries with 3,474 cases including 54 deaths on February 27. WHO raises the risk of the spread of COVID-19 from "high" to "very high".

According to doctors and health experts, the Coronavirus's symptoms are similar to those of the Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome (SARS), but with such a gloomy picture no one is sure enough to predict or tell when the peak of the virus will occur, and for how long it will continue (Donnelly, Malik, Elkholy, Cauchemez, & Van Kerkhove, 2019).

A progression rate of the epidemic to an advanced level of a pandemic has intensified the risk and damage not only at the human fatalities level but also brought so devastating effects and repercussions at all levels: economic, political, social, psychological, etc. Within this complex array of relationships, the present piece of research provides a representation of the Coronavirus outbreak in the English headlines of Reuters and Xinhua.

Review of Relevant Literature

There is a three-way relationship between cognition, ideology and social practices since a cognitive interpretation of a certain ideology leads to a certain social behaviour. This triangle is closely related to the power of the supporting party, be it political, economic, or otherwise, signalling authority and dominance (Van Dijk, 2006). The question of partisanship is discursively interpreted as the result of opposing views and ideologies expressed by the pronominal use of the positive 'us' and the negative 'them'. This is consistent with Van Dijk (2008) polarity strategy to sanction and legitimize the self and to dismiss or delegitimize the other.

Critical discourse analysis, which investigates the relationship between language, power, and society, has gone beyond the purely structural levels of language analysis to include more sophisticated aspects of social practice, intertextuality and multimodality. By expanding the realm of discourse analysis to integrate new methodologies and genres, critical discourse analysis encompassed politics, ethnography, nation, identity, and power relations (Wodak, 2001). In the same vein, Fairclough (1992, p. 64) defines discourse as "any practice that is both semiotic and social." For Fairclough (2001), language is not merely a simple linguistic phenomenon but a social practice. The relationship between ideology, power and hegemony are quite influential in CDA. For Fairclough (2003, p. 218), "ideologies are representations of aspects of the world which contribute to establishing and maintaining relations of power, domination and exploitation."

Media news discourse is one of the main domains of critical discourse analysis, which embraces the social, political, economic, ideological and cognitive aspects of news processing. This orientation lends support to the macro aspect and conditions of news media as a multi-disciplinary system of interactive social practice. This is not to ignore, however, the linguistics aspect of media news reporting where media discourse is to be analyzed at different levels of language restructure, lexical, syntactic, semantic, textual, and contextual.

In news discourse, headlines undoubtedly stand out as one of the most fundamental features of news discourse as they provide a summary of the main information in news items. More often than not, the form and style of the headline can mirror the thematic structure of the news report or story. Sometimes, transparency and objectivity may be overshadowed and mystified by the political affiliation of the source and/or the ideological implications of the headlines, both cognitive and social, targeting a given group of the readership. In this case, the headline may be either biased or prejudiced, which is not a rarity in news coverage. Haider and Hussein (2019) qualitatively examined a headlines corpus of *The Guardian* published in English, and *Asharq Al-Awsat* published in Arabic from 2009 to 2011 and compared the findings with the corpus quantitative analysis of the content of the same articles. The researchers found that the analysis of the headlines revealed complementary and convergent findings with the corpus analysis. The researchers recommended using headlines as a down-sampling method of large corpora. Similarly, in this paper, the researchers investigate a relatively large corpus of headlines to examine how COVID-19 and China are represented in Reuters and Xinhua.

Ellis (2018) investigated how four major U.S. newspapers framed the Swine Flu Virus in Mexico in Spring 2009. The researcher used qualitative content analysis and found that fear and othering were present and dominant in the U.S. coverage of the virus. Moodley and Lesage (2019) examined how the Ebola virus is represented in South African news reports from March 2014 to June 2015. The researchers used Parker's (1992) guidelines for analysis to identify the ways and discourses of how the disease was constructed. After excluding

the medical discourse of reporting, the researchers found four social discourses, namely threat to humanity, predation, invasion, and conspiracy. The present paper's representation of the Coronavirus-19 in news headlines shows some resemblance to this one. But where the Ebola virus disease (EVD) affected only three African countries causing 28,103 cases and 11,290 deaths, Coronavirus-19 is markedly different in terms of global spread, the number of cases and deaths which continue to mount.

Methodology

The news articles, comprising the data for this study were compiled through Factiva News Database. News articles on "2019-nCoV" (Coronavirus-19) were collected from two major news sources, namely Reuters News Agency, and Xinhua, the biggest and most influential media organization in China. The authors' choice for Reuters and Xinhua as data collection sources derives from the magnitude and influence of the two agencies as major media and press outlets with a high level of accessibility, international services and coverage. Huang, ElTayeb, Zolnoori, and Yao (2018, p. 3) pointed out that "Reuters media is a leading global information and news agency and the world's largest international text and television news provider". As the Press outlet of the Chinese Communist Party (CCP), Xinhua was founded in 1931, and it is the official state-run press agency. Besides Chinese, it publishes in 9 languages including English. Feng, Brewer, and Ley (2012, p. 257) argued that "news organizations in China typically follow Xinhua's agenda, and almost all of the mainstream print media and major television channels rely on its feeds". Being known for their influence, the two agencies are keen to provide comprehensive coverage of international events. This is particularly important for this very event, the "2019-nCoV", whose consequences and repercussions will be affecting the international community. In addition, the choice has been motivated by the authors' pursuit to compile their corpus from different sources, one of which is Chinese.

It is noteworthy that for the articles to be included in the corpus, they should occur in the specified time span, particularly January 8, 2020, when the first article on the virus is published to February 29, 2020, when other countries, especially in Europe, became the epicentre of the epidemic. For the article to be included in the corpus, it should include the following query term, namely: coronavirus. It is worth mentioning that duplicate articles were excluded.

The search resulted in 16,980 articles; 3019 of which are published in January and 13,961 in February as Table 1 shows.

Table 1. Number of articles in Reuters and Xinhua from January 8 to February 29

Month	Date	Nu. of articles in Reuters	Nu. of articles in Xinhua	Month	Date	Nu. of articles in Reuters	Nu. of articles in Xinhua	
January				February	1	127	73	
					2	156	51	
					3	492	102	
					4	535	107	
					5	490	104	
		8	1		0	6	465	104
		9	5		3	7	502	122
		10	3		0	8	129	77
		11	6		2	9	128	82
		12	4		0	10	452	119
		13	11		3	11	506	120
		14	12		3	12	506	107
		15	11		2	13	539	116
		16	6		3	14	489	122
		17	15		4	15	96	107
		18	14		0	16	108	59
		19	19		3	17	319	110
		20	47		16	18	472	107
		21	200		17	19	427	116
		22	257		45	20	512	128
		23	329		40	21	508	152

24	281	29	22	147	53
25	104	45	23	158	81
26	123	50	24	612	119
27	343	61	25	676	122
28	435	78	26	840	105
29	531	55	27	954	128
30	507	81	28	998	115
31	572	66	29	322	89
Total	3836	606	Total	12665	2997
Duplicates	1329	94	Duplicates	4266	454
Total	2507	512		8399	2543
16,980 Articles					

Research Procedures:

The procedures followed in this study are:

Step 1: Writing the research questions. Three research questions were designed.

Step 2: Compiling an appropriate corpus. A corpus of news articles from Xinhua and Reuters was compiled using Factiva. 2 sub-corpora of the headlines of the articles were designed.

Step 3: Using Wordsmith 6 (WS6) (Scott, 2012) which is a corpus linguistic software designed by Mike Scott to generate a frequency list of the headlines in the two news agencies. The researchers will only examine the most frequent lexical words to uncover the news foci in the headlines of the two news agencies.

Step 4: grouping the most frequent 30 words in Reuters and Xinhua news in different thematic categories.

Step 5: Carrying out a concordance analysis (KWIC: Keyword in Context) to investigate how the words in the different thematic groups are used in the headlines.

Step 6: Carrying out a collocation analysis for China within the boundaries of headlines and specifying the collocation span as ± 5 words (five words on either side of the node word). The researchers examined the most salient 20 collocates.

Step 7: Examining the verbs that occurred with China as a subject, and the nouns that followed China's

Step 8: Conducting a qualitative concordance analysis for some of the results obtained in steps 6 and 7.

Step 9: Linking the findings with the existing literature and trying to interpret and explain the findings using some theoretical frameworks.

Data analysis and findings

Ever since the Coronavirus-19 outbreak was first reported from Wuhan, China, late December 2019, media news networks have been racing around-the-clock to report breaking news and updates. Of the most prominent news agencies providing comprehensive coverage on the novel virus spread, impact, and consequences, repercussions of the coronavirus outbreak are Reuters and Xinhua, the biggest New China Chinese Agency. Upon tracking and analyzing the coverage of the virus outbreak by the two leading news hubs, the authors identified and targeted some key domains, which have been directly and heavily influenced by the Coronavirus-19 crisis.

Our data collection started on January 8, when WHO officially announced the virus outbreak. The outbreak was declared a Public Health Emergency of International Concern on 30 January 2020. We chose February 29 as the end-date when we reached the point where the virus has tailed off and spread globally affecting over 160 countries, despite the ongoing spread of Coronavirus-19 beyond this date.

Frequency Analysis

To identify the most frequently discussed topics by the two news agencies under study, the researchers generated a list of the most frequent 30 content words in the two corpora of headlines as figure 1 shows. It is worth pointing out that the researchers used a stop list to filter out the function words and the words that are related to the names of sections of the two news agencies.

Figure 1. The most frequent 30 words in Reuters and Xinhua news agencies

Reuters			Xinhua		
N	Word	Freq.	N	Word	Freq.
1	coronavirus	4,221	1	china	1,351
2	china	2,281	2	coronavirus	1,020
3	virus	1,577	3	epidemic	460
4	says	1,324	4	novel	443
5	new	684	5	chinese	335
6	outbreak	669	6	outbreak	283
7	fears	652	7	fight	262
8	cases	551	8	new	244
9	stocks	545	9	cases	241
10	health	491	10	control	186
11	impact	474	11	wuhan	169
12	reports	343	12	confirmed	149
13	oil	308	13	hubei	138
14	global	306	14	reports	136
15	hit	281	15	virus	133
16	low	281	16	patients	124
17	chinese	275	17	infection	114
18	demand	262	18	support	112
19	shares	255	19	battle	105
20	case	249	20	official	100
21	first	248	21	pneumonia	98
22	fall	247	22	world	98
23	who	230	23	medical	97
24	growth	224	24	case	88
25	rise	214	25	xi	84
26	spread	214	26	measures	78
27	asia	210	27	efforts	73
28	wuhan	203	28	beijing	70
29	flights	202	29	says	68
30	japan	198	30	hong	66

As Van Dijk (1997, p. 9) puts it, “a text is merely a tip of iceberg and it is the responsibility of the discourse analysts to uncover the hidden meaning of the text”. Guided by this interdisciplinary approach of multi-modality, the researchers grouped the most frequent 30 words in Reuters and Xinhua news in six categories: (1) outbreak of the virus, (2) places (3) reporting verbs and officials, (4) number of cases, (5) repercussions (psychological, economic, transportation...), and (6) fighting the virus as table 2 shows. It is worth noting that the author first examined the most frequent 100 content words, and found the same categories observed in Table 2.

Table 2. Thematic categories of the most frequent 30 words in Reuters and Xinhua

Thematic Category	Reuters	Xinhua
Outbreak of the virus	Coronavirus, virus, new, outbreak	coronavirus, epidemic, novel, outbreak, new, virus, infection, pneumonia
Places	China, Chinese, who, Asia, Wuhan, japan	china, Chinese, Wuhan, Hubei, Beijing, world, Hong
Reporting verbs and officials	says	confirmed, reports, says, official, xi
Number of cases	cases, hit, case, health, global, spread	cases, patients
Repercussions (psychological, economic, transportation...)	fears, impact, flights, stocks, oil, demand, shares, low, fall, growth, rise	
Fighting the virus		fight, control, battle, support, measures, efforts

To shed light on the differences between Reuters’ and Xinhua’s coverage of the Covid-19 crisis, the researchers examined the categories that were unique in one news agency but were not common in the other. The major theme featuring the discourse domains which have been directly impacted by the outbreak in Reuters was “repercussions” concerning economy, transportation, and psychological effects. On the other hand, “fighting the virus” was a dominant discourse theme in Xinhua when compared to Reuters.

Unique themes discussed in Reuters’ reporting

In this section, the researchers carry out a concordance analysis (KWIC) for the words listed in the “repercussions” category, and how they were used in Reuters. The words represented in this category include

fears, impact, flights, stocks, oil, demand, shares, low, fall, growth, and rise. These words have been further divided into 3 subcategories, namely psychological effect, economy, and transportation (Table 3). To highlight the differences between the two news agencies, Table 3 also shows the raw and normalized frequency of these words. The raw frequency refers to how many times the word occurs in the corpus, while the normalized frequency refers to the word occurrences per one thousand words.

Table 3. The frequency of words in the “Repercussions” category

Repercussions	Reuters	Raw Freq.	Normalized Freq.	Xinhua	Raw Freq.	Normalized Freq.
Economy	stocks	545	0.46	stocks	17	0.06
	impact	474	0.40	impact	26	0.09
	oil	308	0.26	oil	7	0.06
	low	281	0.24	low	3	0.01
	demand	262	0.22	demand	15	0.05
	shares	255	0.22	shares	8	0.03
	fall	247	0.21	fall	3	0.01
	growth	224	0.19	growth	10	0.03
	rise	214	0.18	rise	25	0.08
Transportation	flights	202	0.17	flights	24	0.08
Psychological effect	fears	652	0.55	fears	11	0.04

The economic dimension seems to dominate this category where 9 out of 11 words representing the ‘repercussions’ category belong to the economic domain. The economic power and the world’s markets were among the most directly and heavily affected by the Coronavirus-19 outbreak. The impact was most evidently reflected in Reuters’ high frequency reporting on leading world economies and financial markets. The researchers carried out a concordance analysis for the word *impact* that has neutral connotations and the word *growth* which has positive connotations (concordance 1 and concordance 2).

Concordance 1. Analysis of *growth* and *impact* in Reuters

N	Concordance
1 <title> REFILE-Singapore downgrades 2020 growth forecast due to coronavirus outbreak </title>
2	Slovenia's GDP growth slows in 2019, coronavirus could hurt 2020 growth </title>
3 <title> Switzerland will lower economic growth forecasts over coronavirus </title>
4 <title> Coronavirus to trim French growth by 0.1 points: minister </title>
5	<title> Apple warns sales to fall short of target due to coronavirus impact </title>
6	<title> New Zealand says can manage coronavirus impact on economy </title>
7	German car registrations expected to fall further due to coronavirus impact </title>
8 <title> Coronavirus impact on financial markets and economies </title>
9	<title> RPT-Saudi Aramco CEO expects coronavirus impact on oil demand to be short-lived </title>
10 <title> BOJ official warns of coronavirus impact on Japan's economy </title>
11	<title> Trump's national security adviser says coronavirus could impact U.S.-China trade deal -CNN </title>
12	<title> G20 ready to adopt policies to limit economic impact of coronavirus -Saudi </title>
13 <title> Companies feel impact of coronavirus outbreak in China </title>
14 <title> Nike warns of financial impact from coronavirus outbreak </title>
15	<title> Mexican official says coronavirus outbreak in China may impact financial conditions </title>
16 <title> Italy's PM Conte says impact of coronavirus on economy could be "very strong" </title>

A careful study of the Reuters’ examples in concordance 1 dismisses any positive short-term prospects for the world economy. The picture is gloomy and the worst is yet to come if the coronavirus predicament continues to pose a threat and a decline in the international markets, trade and industries, the backbone of the world’s economic power. This seems to be the case in the foreseeable future especially with the surge in the Coronavirus cases in the U.S. and Europe, together with WHO’s declaring the coronavirus outbreak a pandemic. It is noteworthy however that Reuters’ balanced, neutral, and unbiased reporting approach continues to present news as is without embellishment or partisanship. This is evidenced in citations 6 and 9 of Concordance 1 which mitigate the virus impact on the world economy: “New Zealand’s says can manage coronavirus impact on economy,” and “Saudi Aramco CEO expects coronavirus impact on oil demand to be short-lived” (6 and 9 respectively).

Since the outbreak of the virus in December 2019, the 2020 economic growth forecast in some countries such as Singapore, Slovenia, and Switzerland, among others, is downgraded and lowered (lines 1, 2, and 3). The economies of some other countries will be affected as well (lines 4, 10, and 16). The virus impacted different industries including, but not limited to, tech companies (line 5), auto industry (line 7), oil (line 9), and sportswear manufacturing companies (14). It has also affected or may further affect world trade and businesses (lines 11, 13).

From a critical discourse analysis perspective (CDA), Concordance 1 data (lines 2, 3, 6, 11, 15, 16) show that ‘modality’, indicated by the use of modal verbs as *may, can, could, will*, etc., has been heavily used in this category. This suggests that, with this condition of uncertainty, further complications of the economic situation may be in sight. Another aspect of the CDA representation is the use of ‘authority and power’ expressions reflected in the words ‘minister, CEO, advisor, PM, Officials, which gives the news a kind of credibility (Concordance 1, lines 4, 9, 10, 11, 15, and 16).

On the other hand, and to depict Xinhua’s reporting and coverage of the Coronavid-19 impact on the world economy, the researchers conducted a parallel concordance analysis for the words *growth* and *impact* in Xinhua’s corpus (concordance 2).

Concordance 2. Analysis of *growth* and *impact* in Xinhua

N	Concordance
1 <title> Long-term economic growth fundamentals unchanged: Xi </title>
2 <title> China's digital marketing industry maintains growth amid epidemic </title>
3 <title> Novel coronavirus impact not to reverse growth of China's economy: Chinese state councilor </title>
4	Experts say China's economy resilient enough to withstand coronavirus impact </title>
5 <title> Coronavirus impact on Chinese economy to be limited: official </title>
6	<title> Greek business leaders express optimism over coronavirus impact , officials suggest calm </title>
7 <title> Coronavirus epidemic impact will be temporary, limited: China's forex regulator </title>
8 <title> Epidemic unlikely to heavily impact China's financial system: official </title>
9 <title> China capable of minimizing impact of epidemic on economy: spokesperson </title>
10 <title> U.S. economist says impact of COVID-19 on Chinese, world economy limited </title>

Going through the incidents in Xinhua, it can be inferred that the news agency tends to present an optimistic outlook towards the economic impact of the coronavirus outbreak on the global economy. For Xinhua, the overall assessment of the economic situation is positive and, according to the Chinese President Xi, ‘the long-term economic growth fundamentals remain unchanged’ (line 1). Xinhua’s coverage confirms that the virus may only have a short-term impact on the resilient Chinese economy, financial system, digital marketing and industry. The news agency quoted some Chinese and non-Chinese officials to highlight this aspect. For example Xi, the President of the People’s Republic of China, Chinese state councillor, China’s forex regulator and some other officials stressed that the impact of the virus is temporary and limited on the Chinese economy (lines 1, 3, 5, 7, 8, and 9). Some non-Chinese economists, experts, and business leaders were supportive as they stressed the same idea (lines 4, 6 and 10). Xinhua’s positive-self representation of China in the news resides in the fact that the news agency operates under government control and its releases reflect the countries’ official policy. Such self-esteem, confidence, and assertiveness of China’s adoption of well-thought-out health, economic, and other policies to contain the spread of the virus have been a trend in Xinhua’s reporting. This has been reflected in the heavy emphasis on China’ measures in fighting the virus spread, together with the endorsement of other countries supportive of China’s handling of the virus crisis.

The second aspect in the repercussion category that received heavy coverage is ‘air transport’. Reuters’ data showed a heavy emphasis on air travel, which has been massively influenced by the COVID-19 outbreak. Most international airline carriers have either suspended, cancelled or reduced their flights to destinations hit by the coronavirus. Such measures are meant to reduce contacts with people who may be potential carriers of the virus. But these massive reductions in air travel operations harshly affected the economy of the countries involved. Transport, which provides for and is associated with all other modern life needs, is an essential source of support for a booming economy as it facilitates mobility worldwide. This mobility was hampered, especially when the largest majority of airlines have either suspended, cancelled, or reduced their operations. Such measures have largely affected the tourism industry, especially with the high percentage of group cancellations in this sector. According to Reuters’ corpus, Abu Dhabi Etihad, Lebanon, Taiwan, Pakistan, South Korea Airlines, the Czech government, Ukraine, Qantas, Delta, Bulgaria Air, Germany’s Lufthansa, Qantas, Egypt Air, Kenya Airways, Indonesian Lion Air Group, among others, have suspended flights to China and other countries with coronavirus (Concordance 3).

Concordance 3. Analysis of *flights* in Reuters

N	Concordance
1 <title> Abu Dhabi's Etihad suspends flights to Hong Kong on low demand </title>
2 <title> Lebanon restricts flights to countries with coronavirus, halts pilgrimage trips
3 <title> Taiwan to suspend most flights to mainland China to control coronavirus </title>
4 <title> Pakistan halts flights to and from China: civil aviation authority </title>
5 <title> S.Korean airlines halt flights to Daegu, city with most virus cases </title>
6 <title> Czech government bans direct flights to China, effective February 9 </title>
7 <title> Ukraine to stop direct flights to China from Feb. 4 </title>
8	<title> Singapore starts screening all China flights , warns against Wuhan travel to deter coronavirus
9 <title> Qantas suspends China flights from Feb 9 due to coronavirus </title>
10	<title> Delta says it will suspend all U.S.- China flights </title>
11 <title> Bulgaria Air Cancels flights to Milan over coronavirus </title>
12 <title> Germany's Lufthansa Cancels flights to China due to coronavirus - Bild </title>
13 <title> Egyptair to suspend all flights to and from China over Coronavirus </title>
14 <title> Kenya Airways suspends all flights to China amid coronavirus outbreak </title>
15	<title> Indonesia's Lion Air Group to suspend all flights to China from February </title>

A close look at the Reuter data suggests that transport, and air travel, in particular, has sustained big losses resulting from Coronavid-2019.

To see how the subcategory of “transportation” is represented in the Chinese News Agency, the researchers carried out a concordance for the word “flight” (Concordance 4).

Concordance 4. Analysis of *flights* in Xinhua

N	Concordance
1 <title> Airlines begin canceling Italy flights amid coronavirus outbreak </title>
2	<title> China Southern Airlines resumes over 2,100 domestic flights amid epidemic </title>
3 <title> Charter flights bring home 310 Hubei residents from abroad: Foreign Ministry
4 <title> UAE suspends all Iran flights following COVID-19 outbreak </title>
5 <title> Suspending flights not to help curb epidemic, but sow panic: spokesperson
6 <title> Hong Kong to arrange two flights to bring back residents on quarantined ship in Japan </title>
7 <title> Charter flights to bring home 2,000 Chinese tourists from the Philippines
8 <title> Iraqi Airways suspends flights with Iran over Coronavirus </title>
9 <title> Italy agrees to resume some flights with China </title>
10 <title> China's civil flights won't be suspended: FM spokesperson </title>

Unlike Reuters’ reporting on the air travel situation, Xinhua’s coverage focused on those responses that reduce the impact of the COVID-19 outbreak on the aviation sector. Instead of highlighting suspensions of international flights to China, the news agency diverted attention to flight cancellations to other countries hit by the virus such as Italy, Iran (lines 1, 4 and 8). On the other hand, Xinhua highlighted the resumption of 2100 domestic flights (line 2), charter flights bringing home 310 Hubei residents from abroad (3), Charter flights to bring home 2000 Chinese tourists from the Philippines (7), Italy resumes flights with China (9), and China’s civil flights will not be suspended (10). Again, Xinhua’s emphasis on the limited impact of the coronavirus on the air travel sector, while targeting other countries, is consistent with China’s official policy adopted by Xinhua to applaud the Chinese government’s sound decisions. For Xinhua, China’s robust economy is formidable enough to absorb and withstand any emerging conditions.

The third aspect in the repercussion category is ‘psychological effect’. The COVID-19 outbreak was appallingly terrifying to the entire international community especially when many countries, in addition to China, have become coronavirus hot spots such as South Korea, Italy, Iran, the Middle East, and many European countries, the U.S. and Canada. Fears have escalated over the increasing number of new cases and a rising death toll. WHO’s declaring COVID-19 outbreak a pandemic, aroused fears where US stocks struggled, and banks making emergency rate cuts to counter the coronavirus shock. Amidst this state of chaos, many countries have taken strict and immediate measures calling for the ban public gatherings, cancellation of major sports events, economic forums, conferences, etc. Some countries have suspended regular classes in their educational systems until further notice, and others resorted to distance education platforms as an option.

Reuters’ corpus of data for this study contained ample evidence in support of the escalating state of anxiety, fear and psychological stress leading to panic. Examples, retrieved from Reuters’ corpus are shown in concordance 5 below:

Concordance 5. Analysis of *fears* in Reuters

N	Concordance
1	<title> IBM withdraws from RSA conference over coronavirus fears </title>
2	<title> N. Korea to cancel April marathon over coronavirus fears -tour company </title>
3	Korea's K-League postpones matches over coronavirus fears </title>
4	<title> Facebook cancels San Francisco summit on coronavirus fears </title>
5	Mobile World Congress in Barcelona called off over coronavirus fears </title>
6 <title> Cotton plunges over 4% as coronavirus fears grip markets </title>
7	<title> Oil prices dive to lowest in over a year on coronavirus fears </title>
8	<title> Iraq's Sadr suspends protest call over coronavirus fears - statement </title>
9	<title> North Korea suspends foreign tourism over coronavirus fears: tour companies </title>
10	Tennis-Fed Cup group moved out of China over coronavirus fears </title>
11	Russia postpones annual investment forum over coronavirus fears </title>
12 <title> Indian shares slip on fears over fast-spreading coronavirus; metal stocks fall
13	<title> Russia strengthens sanitary controls at borders over virus fears - Ifax cites watchdog </title>
14 <title> Expats across China flee as virus fears mount </title>
15	Tokyo postpones training for Olympics volunteers over virus fears </title>

The above citations provide solid evidence in support of the thesis that Coronavid-19 is a real threat where the psychological effect and accompanying fears are mounting to create a state of panic and anxiety at a global level. Local, national, and international events, activities, have been cancelled, suspended, or postponed. This was evidenced in a variety of sectors including Business Machine Organizations (IBM) and Facebook, Mobile World Congress (lines 1, 4, 5). Sports and athletic events were impacted as well, including North Korea’s April marathon, Korea’s K-League matches, Tennis-Fed Cup group, and Tokyo’s training for Olympics volunteers (lines 2, 3, 10, 15). Fears and concerns triggered by demand for basic needs affecting national and global economy such as cotton, oil, and tourism, shares, investment forums, lack of sanitation control, etc. were major causes of unrest and psychological stress and unrest (lines 6, 7, 11, 12, and 13). Expat’s across China fleeing, as virus mounts (line 14) is a true representation of the psychological effects of the coronavirus outbreak on people.

Contrary to Reuters’ reporting on people’s anxiety and psychological conditions, Xinhua’s reporting was more assuring by downplaying the negative effects of the COVID-19 on China and the world economy at large. For example, they described the oil prices as ‘bouncing back amid easing virus fears (1); the rise of the U.S. dollar as virus fears ease (2); NY officials dine in Chinatown(3); U.S. cities rally behind Chinatowns (4); response to epidemic should be based on science, not fears (5) overcome fake fear in China-U.S. relations with foresight (6); San Francisco mayor urges public confidence in Chinatown business (7); and ‘Across China: Mental health care volunteers dispel coronavirus-caused fears, anxiety, in communities (8) (Concordance 6).

Concordance 6. Analysis of *fears* in Xinhua

N	Concordance
1 <title> Roundup: Weekly oil prices bounce back amid easing virus fears, output cut </title>
2 <title> U.S. dollar rises as virus fears ease </title>
3 <title> Spotlight: NYC officials dine in Chinatowns to help shatter fear over COVID-19 </title>
4 <title> Feature: U.S. cities rally behind Chinatowns, quell fears of COVID-19 </title>
5 <title> Response to epidemic should be based on science, not fear: FM spokesperson </title>
6 <title> Commentary: Overcome fake fear in China-U.S. relations with foresight </title>
7	San Francisco mayor urges public confidence in Chinatown businesses amid coronavirus fears </title>
8	<title> Across China: Mental health care volunteers dispel coronavirus-caused fears, anxiety in communities </title>

In sum, Xinhua's analysis of fears in all Concordance 6 examples focused on the CDA principle of 'us vs. them'. The Chinese news agency is trying to alleviate the impact of the virus outbreak by depicting the condition as a transitional period which will not have any serious repercussions either on the Chinese economy or even the world economy. They cite examples of the recovery of the Chinese economy while emphasizing the strength of U.S.-China trade relations. For China, the country's growing global role, economic power, pride and self-esteem are at stake. The same was reflected in Xinhua's reporting on China's management of the virus crisis, which –according to them– was characterized with the highest level of professionalism, efficiency and tactfulness to reassure China's industrial might and supremacy.

Main themes discussed in Xinhua's reporting

The category of "Fighting the Virus" was remarkably dominant in Xinhua's coverage. It included many words, which referred to ways and means of combating and curbing the epidemic, such as *fight*, *control*, *battle*, *support*, *measures*, and *efforts*. Table 4 shows the frequency of words in this category in both Xinhua and Reuters.

Table 4. The frequency of words in the category of "Fighting the Virus"

Xinhua	Raw Freq.	Normalized Freq.	Reuters	Raw Freq.	Normalized Freq.
fight	262	0.89	fight	64	0.05
control	186	0.63	control	47	0.04
support	112	0.38	support	72	0.06
battle	105	0.36	battle	15	0.01
measures	78	0.26	measures	89	0.08
efforts	73	0.25	efforts	21	0.02

Amidst this state of fear, panic, strict and preventive measures, caution, and suspense, the international community pledged to stand unified in combating the vicious virus. Global efforts have been exerted by health organizations, NGOs, public and private sectors, and people united to win the battle against this fierce virus. Medical centres, leading pharmaceutical companies are sparing no effort to develop a vaccine for the killer virus. This has been evidenced in the terminology used by the two news agencies in their coverage and reporting on actions and measures taken to curb the coronavirus outbreak. The following Xinhua's examples highlight the world's collective efforts battling the virus (Concordance 7).

Concordance 7. Analysis of *Battle*, *control*, *fight*, *measures* and *support* in Xinhua

N	Concordance
1 <title> China appreciates Pakistan's support to battle against coronavirus: FM </title>
2	<title> Roundup: World leaders positively evaluate, support China's fight against virus outbreak </title>
3	<title> Turkish businessman donates 20,000 USD to support China's battle against Coronavirus </title>
4	<title> Ugandan president optimistic about China's measures to contain coronavirus </title>
5 <title> Putin praises China's "decisive, vigorous" measures to fight novel coronavirus outbreak </title>
6	<title> Chinese people show patriotism in coronavirus fight: spokesperson </title>
7 <title> Donation from 11 countries to fight coronavirus arrives in China </title>
8 <title> UN chief confident in China's effort to fight coronavirus outbreak </title>
9 <title> NBA stars show support for China in fight against virus </title>
10	<title> Council of African Political Parties chief hails China's efforts to contain coronavirus </title>
11 <title> Cambodian PM lauds China's efforts to contain spread of COVID-19 </title>
12 <title> China to audit coronavirus control funds, donations </title>
13	<title> Confident novel coronavirus outbreak under control by late April: health expert </title>
14	China promotes TV, radio shows to rally morale in coronavirus battle </title>
15	<title> Across China: Italians confident about China's battle against coronavirus </title>
16	<title> Feature: Japan offers warm support to China in battle against virus outbreak </title>
17	<title> China Focus: Foreigners positive, confident in battle against virus in east China province </title>

Xinhua's coverage showed how the international community was supportive and appreciative of China's ingenuity and wisdom in handling the COVID-19 crises. This support was expressed in many ways and on different levels. The UN chief, world leaders and top officials, international organizations, and different countries praised China's remarkable response, efforts and stunning speed in controlling the virus (lines 2, 4, 5, 8, 9, 10, 11, 15, and 17). For its part, China reacted with great appreciation to the support of the international community and their confidence in China's strong economy, people's decisiveness, solidarity, and nationalism (lines 1 and 6).

To see how the category of "Fighting the Virus" is represented in Reuters, the researchers also carried out a concordance analysis for the words *battle*, *control*, *fight*, *measures* and *support* (concordance 8).

Concordance 8. Analysis of *battle*, *control*, *fight*, *measures* and *support* in Reuters

N	Concordance
1 <title> Battle against coronavirus turns to Italy; Wall Street falls on pandemic fears
2 <title> U.S. Senate Democrats seeking at least \$3.1 bln to battle coronavirus </title>
3 <title> China's Xi says coronavirus control the most important task </title>
4 <title> China's epidemic control is showing an improving trend- state media </title>
5	<title> Hong Kong extends school suspension until April 20 to control spread of coronavirus </title>
6	<title> Taiwan to suspend most flights to mainland China to control coronavirus </title>
7 <title> Trump says coronavirus under control in the U.S. </title>
8 <title> Trump: U.S. appreciates China's 'efforts and transparency' on coronavirus </title>
9 <title> Pope Francis praises China's efforts to contain coronavirus </title>
10	UPDATE 3-Japan PM Abe seeks citizens' help in coronavirus fight as Olympics to go ahead </title>
11 <title> Trump's request for \$2.5 billion to fight coronavirus 'inadequate', Pelosi says </title>
12 <title> World Bank not considering new China loans to fight coronavirus, president says </title>
13 <title> China allocates \$10.26 billion to fight coronavirus </title>
14 <title> Italy's Lombardy says emergency coronavirus measures must be extended </title>
15 <title> China to Russia: End discriminatory coronavirus measures against Chinese </title>
16 <title> Germany discussing measures in case coronavirus hits economy - Altmaier </title>
17 <title> Moscow imposes special safety measures at tourist sites over coronavirus fears </title>
18 <title> WHO: global community not ready to take same measures as China to contain coronavirus </title>
19 <title> Germany enacts new health security measures against coronavirus infections </title>
20	e> S.Korea stocks bounce as virus spread slows, govt pledges support </title>
21 <title> EU medicines agency to support coronavirus vaccine, drug development </title>
22 <title> China issues measures to support manufacturers, businesses hit by coronavirus </title>
23 <title> UPDATE 2-China's central bank vows to step up support for virus-hit economy </title>

As Concordance 8 shows, Reuter's reporting was balanced showing how China's measures in fighting the coronavirus were successful, something which was acknowledged and commended by other countries and their leaders. For example, line 4 above refers to the improving trend in China's control of the virus spread. Similarly, line 8 highlights U.S. President Trump's appreciation of China's efforts and transparency on coronavirus. The same is expressed by Pope Francis's praise of China's efforts to contain coronavirus (line 9). Further acknowledgement of Chin's efforts in fighting the virus comes from WHO stressing that "global

community is not ready to take same measures as China to contain coronavirus (line 18). At the same time, Reuters continues to emphasize China's ongoing efforts to support its national economy as lines 22 and 23 show through measures taken to support manufacturers and businesses hit by the coronavirus; and China's Central Bank vows to step up support for the virus-hit economy. This is consistent with the Chinese President' describing 'coronavirus contrail as the most important task (line 3). Once again, Reuters' coverage reflects a very objective and unbiased stand, a testimony to its credibility and integrity.

But with fears from the killer virus are escalating, many countries including U.S., Russia, Italy, and Germany, Japan, EU, S. Korea, etc., are enacting new health security measures to contain the virus (cf. Concordance 8: Examples 1, 2, 5, 6, 10, 14, 16, 19, 20, 21).

Collocation Analysis

To examine how China is represented in the context of Coronavid-19 in the headlines of both Xinhua and Reuters, the researchers carried out a collocational analysis targeting the most salient 20 collocates as Table 5 shows. Collocates were obtained by using the Z-score within WordSmith's default span of 5 words either side of the target phrase. While WordSmith offers numerous ways of calculating collocates, namely MI, MI3, Z-score, T-score, log-likelihood and rank by frequency, the Z-score was chosen because it tends to favour medium frequency collocates which tend to be lexical nouns.

Table 5. The most salient collocates using the Z-score

Xinhua				Reuters			
N	Word	Z-Score	F.	N	Word	Z-Score	F.
1	Reports	7.99	100	1	Hubei	20.5	137
2	Support	6.21	76	2	Province	16.6	104
3	Fight	5.17	137	3	Flights	15.8	124
4	Confident	5.11	30	4	Virus	14.3	521
5	Sees	4.08	22	5	Epicentre	12.3	44
6	Ensure	4.01	24	6	Deaths	10.3	80
7	Aviation	4	6	7	Mainland	9.68	69
8	Efforts	3.69	43	8	Number	9.03	48
9	Industry	3.63	12	9	Ore	8.98	30
10	Ensures	3.6	10	10	Reports	8.88	123
11	Solidarity	3.56	22	11	Iron	7.98	27
12	Join	3.42	9	12	Suspend	7.62	33
13	Outnumber	3.42	9	13	Stimulus	7.55	36
14	Central	3.39	15	14	Total	6.58	61
15	Confirmed	3.34	74	15	Spreading	6.54	30
16	Helps	3.26	10	16	New	6.17	182
17	Vows	3.26	10	17	Tariff	6.1	10
18	Appreciates	3.22	8	18	Commission	6.1	26
19	Issues	3.08	12	19	Imports	6	19
20	Newly	3.08	12	20	Tariffs	5.79	12

As Table 5 shows, most Xinhua's collocates with China in the above list have positive connotations. Examples of these include *support*, *fight*, *confident*, *efforts*, *ensure*, *solidarity*, *joins*, *helps*, *vows*, and *appreciates*. The other collocates included reporting verbs such as *reports*, *sees*, and *confirmed*. Other words included *aviation*, *industry*, *outnumbered*, *central*, *issues*, and *newly* (Concordance 9). Over and over again, Xinhua spares no effort to commend China's role, maximizing the efforts and minimizing the losses to enhance the positive "US-image", while at the same time not being critical of 'the other'.

Concordance 9. Most salient collocates with China in *Xinhua*

N	Concordance
1	<title> UN appreciates China's effort against novel coronavirus: Guterres </title>
2	<title> China Focus: General aviation helps fight epidemic </title>
3	<title> China central bank raises limit on small bank payments </title>
4	<title> China's central bank voices confidence in fighting epidemic impact </title>
5	<title> IMF chief "confident" that China's economy "remains resilient" </title>
6	<title> China "confident in, capable of" containing, defeating epidemic: NHC </title>
7	<title> China Focus: Foreign companies confident of Chinese market despite coronavirus outbreak </title>
8	<title> India fully confident in China's victory over coronavirus outbreak: FM </title>
9	<title> Roundup: World grows confident in China's victory against novel coronavirus </title>
10	<title> China Focus: Foreigners positive, confident in battle against virus in east China province </title>
11	<title> China's efforts to fight novel coronavirus achieving positive results: envoy </title>
12	<title> UN official lauds China's efforts to combat novel coronavirus </title>
13	> Roundup: World leaders speak highly of, support China's efforts in fighting novel coronavirus </title>
14	<title> China to ensure power supply in battle against novel coronavirus </title>
15	<title> Roundup: Arab health ministers hail China's fight against COVID-19 </title>
16	<title> China helps students studying abroad mitigate epidemic-related obstacles </title>
17	<title> China's digital marketing industry maintains growth amid epidemic </title>
18	<title> China Focus: Overseas Chinese join anti-coronavirus campaign </title>
19	<title> China sees more patients recover from novel coronavirus infection </title>
20	<title> Roundup: Foreign gov'ts, legislative bodies express solidarity, confidence with China on overcoming pneumonia epidemic </title>
21	<title> Jordan's king reaffirms solidarity with China in face of coronavirus </title>
22	<title> Syria voices solidarity with China in fighting new coronavirus </title>
23	<title> Roundup: World leaders positively evaluate, support China's fight against virus outbreak </title>
24	<title> China never forgets support from Ethiopia in fighting coronavirus: ambassador </title>
25	<title> Xinhua Headlines: China wins global support for epidemic fight </title>
26	<title> China to provide support to countries with weaker health systems: FM spokesperson </title>

As Concordance 9 shows, Xinhua's collocates with China are a testimony to the news agency's outright support of the van Dijk's 'Us vs. Them' CDA principle. Collocational paradigms of the kind evidenced in citations 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 11, 12, 14, 15, 17, 18; 20, 12, 22, 25 express solidarity, confidence with china; (e.g., China's efforts; fight epidemic; voice confidence in fighting epidemic; resilient Chinese economy; capable of containing, fighting epidemic; confident of the Chinese market; fully confident in China's victory over coronavirus outbreak; confident in china's victory against the novel virus; efforts to fight novel coronavirus achieving positive results; China's efforts to combat novel coronavirus; China to ensure power supply in the battle against the novel coronavirus; hail China's fight against COVID-1; Chinese join anti coronavirus campaign; reaffirms solidarity with China; voices solidarity with china; wins global support for epidemic fight).

Some of *China's* collocates in Reuters are related to Chinese places like *Hubei, province* and *mainland*. Although the word *virus* is a frequent word in the corpus, it was a salient collocate with China that is said to be the *epicentre* of the disease. Some words that have negative connotations were salient in the list, and these include *deaths* and *suspend*, and *spreading*. The economic aspect is also reflected in the collocates as the words *ore, iron, Tariff, imports, and Tariff* show. The researchers have also carried out a concordance analysis for China's collocates as shown in Concordance 10.

Concordance 10. The most salient collocates with China in *Reuters*

N	Concordance
1	Saudi Arabia, UAE caution oil market against gloom over China virus </title>
2 <title> Brent logs worst weekly loss in a year as China virus fears swell </title>
3 <title> South African rand weaker in early trade on China virus scare </title>
4 <title> China virus scare sends shudder through European luxury goods sector
5 <title> U.S. must be 'understanding' if China virus impacts trade pledges -agriculture secretary </title>
6 <title> Australia shares gain amid China virus fears </title>
7 <title> Japan stocks erase gains as China virus fears offset tech earnings hopes </title>
8 <title> China virus causes scare for India's smartphone makers </title>
9 <title> How to cope with China virus? Stay in and see 'The Flu' </title>
10 <title> White House adviser says China virus to delay U.S. export surge from trade deal </title>
11 <title> WRAPUP 8-China virus spreads to U.S., curbing travel plans and spooking markets
12 <title> Rouble firms as China halves U.S. import tariffs and virus fears ease </title>
13 <title> China to halve tariffs on some U.S. imports as coronavirus risks grow </title> ..
14 <title> China steel futures rise on stimulus measures, easing of travel curbs </title>
15 <title> China iron ore futures snap 10-day rally amid pandemic fears </title>
16 <title> Wall Street jumps as China stimulus measures soothe virus worries </title>
17 <title> Russia's Magnit suspends fruit and veg imports from China over virus fears - RIA </title>
18 <title> Indonesia says to stop livestock imports from China </title>
19 <title> Chinese Premier Li visits Wuhan, epicentre of virus outbreak </title>
20 <title> Hospitals in China's virus epicentre launch public appeals for supplies </title>
21 <title> A mother's fight for toddler stranded in China's coronavirus epicentre </title>

Unlike Xinhua's positive discourses of China, Reuters' list of collocates portrays a relatively negative picture of the situation. For example, citations 1, 2,3, 4, 7, 10, 15, (e.g., gloom over china virus; china virus fears swell; china virus scare; virus scare sends shudder; China virus fears offset tech earnings hopes) among others send strong messages to the international community of the gravity of the situation at the economic; China virus to delay U.S. export surge; China iron ore futures snap 10-day rally amid pandemic fears. Nevertheless, Reuters' reporting maintains a balanced stand as shown in citation 16 'Wall Street jumps as China stimulus measures soothe virus worries.

In order to check the actions done or will be done by China in the context of COVID-19, the researchers also examined the verbs that occurred with China as a subject with a minimum frequency of three as Table 6 shows.

Table 6: Verbs with "China" as a subject

Xinhua		Reuters	
Verbs	Frequency	Verbs	Frequency
	report	say	43
	see	report	30
	vow	be	18
	send	have	12
	ensure	confirm	8
China	allocate	China	move
	urge		seek
	tighten		take
	offer		postpone
	stress		urge
	appreciate		argue
	make		place
	release		pledge
	move		ban

strengthen	5	expect	3
take	5	cut	3
call	5	warn	3
extend	5	extend	3
launch	5		
postpone	5		
say	5		
advise	4		
step	4		
suspend	4		
resume	4		
confirm	4		
push	3		
mull	3		
deserve	3		
achieve	3		
put	3		
boost	3		
facilitate	3		
pledge	3		
encourage	3		
stay	3		
speed	3		
open	3		
set	3		
cancel	3		
develop	3		
fight	3		
show	3		

In their analysis, the researchers went through all occurrences of China as a subject in Xinhua and observed that China is praised in one way or another in almost all cases. For example, *China achieved fast detection of COVID-19 cases, tightens measures to curb the spread of the virus, sets up research teams to fight the virus spread, and showed remarkable selfishness in combating the virus* (Concordance 11).

Concordance 11. Verbs with China as a subject in Xinhua

N	Concordance
1	<title> China advises citizens postpone overseas travel amid virus outbreak . </title>
2	<title> China appreciates Germany's objective, calm attitude toward epidemic: Chinese FM . </title>
3	<title> China boosts supervision of market prices . </title>
4	<title> China calls for suspending offline training amid coronavirus outbreak . </title>
5	<title> China encourages workers to join online skills training to fight epidemic . </title>
6	<title> China ensures stable job market amid coronavirus outbreak, moves hiring online . </title>
7	<title> China facilitates resumption of work in livestock sector . </title>
8	<title> China launches service platform for cultural trade amid epidemic . </title>
9	<title> China makes utmost efforts to treat severe novel coronavirus pneumonia patients . </title>
10	<title> China Focus: China moves courts online amid coronavirus epidemic . </title>
11	<title> China mulls more tax cuts to aid virus-hit small, medium businesses . </title>
12	<title> China offers financial aid to poor students affected by epidemic . </title>
13	<title> China offers targeted financing support for virus-hit small firms . </title>
14	<title> China opens more online exhibitions amid virus outbreak . </title>
15	<title> China pledges sufficient funding support for poverty alleviation in epidemic-hit regions . </title>
16	<title> China resumes over 70 pct coal production capacity amid epidemic . </title>
17	<title> China says has full confidence, capability to control epidemic . </title>
18	Economic Watch: China seeks new ways to add jobs amid epidemic control . </title>
19	<title> China sets up research team to combat virus spread . </title>
20	<title> Interview: China shows remarkable coordination, selflessness in fighting novel coronavirus: British business leader .
21	<title> China steps up support for self-employed businesses amid epidemic . </title>
22	<title> China strengthens social assistance for needy people amid epidemic outbreak . </title>
23	<title> China strengthens online science popularization amid epidemic . </title>
24	<title> China stresses auditing coronavirus control funds, donations . </title>
25	<title> China urges certain individuals in US, Taiwan to stop political hype, manipulation using epidemic as excuse
26	<title> China vows measures to ensure energy supply amid epidemic control . </title>

As Concordance 11 examples indicate, the variety of verbs associated with China as subject reflect positive values of self-confidence, power of economy, wise management, sound measures and outstanding planning, supported by a strong economy, and brilliant management. Verbs like *advise*, *appreciate*, *boost*, *encourage*, *ensure*, *facilitate*, *launch*, *offers*, *pledge*, *resume*, *set up*, *step up*, *strengthens*, *stresses*, *urges*, and *vows* were frequent with China in Xinhua (cf. citations 1, 2, 3, 5, 6, 7, 8, 12, 15, 16, 19, 21, 23, 24, 25, 26). Such emphasis on the 'positive self' in Xinhua's representation of China in the news, is consistent with its role as the news outlet operating under the Chinese government's control.

The researchers also carried out a concordance analysis for the verbs associated with China in Reuters (Concordance 12).

Concordance 12. Verbs with China as a subject in Reuters

N	Concordance
1 <title> Taiwan, China argue over flights for stranded Taiwanese in Wuhan </title>
2 <title> China cuts pension, insurance costs to help firms hit by coronavirus </title>
3 <title> China has confidence and capability to win the war against coronavirus: foreign ministry
4 <title> China has not yet accepted U.S. help with coronavirus -White House adviser </title>
5 <title> China moves to limit short selling as virus looms over market reopening </title>
6	<title> GRAINS-Soybeans extend gains as China pledges to fulfill U.S. purchases </title>
7 <title> China says to expand imports of meat, other goods to tackle shortages </title>
8 <title> China says curbs on feed, livestock transport must be minimised amid virus </title>
9 <title> China says U.S. creating, spreading fear after virus outbreak </title>
10 <title> China says U.S. should not overreact on coronavirus outbreak </title>
11 <title> China says overall jobs situation stable amid coronavirus outbreak </title>
12 <title> China says banks' non-performing loan ratios to rise due to virus outbreak </title>
13 <title> China says to accelerate the pace of resuming business - state media </title>
14 <title> China says actively supports virus-hit firms to raise funds via debt instruments </title>
15 <title> China says to support firms to resume production as soon as possible </title>
16 <title> China seeks to boost economy as first virus death reported outside its borders </title>
17	US STOCKS-Futures point to rebound as China seeks to curb virus impact </title>
18 <title> Factbox: China takes major steps to prop up coronavirus-hit economy </title>
19 <title> China warns against travel to U.S., citing unfair treatment in virus control </title>
20 <title> UPDATE 1-China warns of sustained virus impact on poultry, eggs supply </title>

As for Reuters' list of verbs with China as a subject, the choices reflect of a relatively reserved tone in China's affirmation of a powerful economy and superiority. This is reflected in the use of less affirmative verbs such as 'argue, cut, say, seek, take, warn' (line 1, 2, 7, 17, 18, 19). But again, Reuters cites examples with verbs which still reflect China's confidence in its ability to act and alleviate the impact of the virus on the country's economy. This is shown in the following examples: 'China has confidence and capability to win the war against coronavirus (3); China pledges to fulfil U.S. purchases (6); China seeks to boost the economy (16). To iterate, this is another piece of evidence in support of Reuters' adherence to and compliance with neutrality, commitment, and professionalism.

Likewise, the researchers examined the nouns that occurred at the L1 position of *China's* with a minimum frequency of three, as Table 7 shows.

Table 7: nouns with "China's"

Xinhua		Reuters	
Word	F	Word	F
fight	90	province	34
Hubei	42	Wuhan	34
effort	27	Hubei	27
battle	14	Xi	16
Wuhan	13	city	12
economy	8	economy	8
bank	7	coronavirus	7
measure	7	China's	Number
victory	6	Number	6
industry	6	outbreak	5
China's	firm	Tianjin	4
PMI	5	market	4
market	5	clampdown	3
sector	4	epicentre	3
legislature	3	virus	3
hub	3	effort	3
SOE	3	response	3
province	3		
transport	3		
news	3		
sale	3		
control	3		

As for the representation of China through identifying the nouns that come immediately after the word China forming an s-genitive construction, Concordances 13 and 14 below furnish a corpus of data which sheds light on the nature of this rapprochement. At the outset, Xinhua’s data depict a very vibrant picture of China’s unparalleled success in making strides curbing the spread of the epidemic. For example, the use of noun phrase of the kind “China’s victory over coronavirus outbreak (1), China’s victory against novel coronavirus (2), China’s fight against epidemic (5), epidemic unlikely to batter China’s economy (9), ... express confidence in China’s battle against the epidemic. Xinhua’s unlimited supportive of the Chinese government’s efforts is evidenced in headlines such as “You are not alone” – countries worldwide offer support, aid to China’s fight against coronavirus.” If anything, this is a testimony to Xinhua’s role in mobilizing the public opinion by having the Chinese people rally behind their government, with a strong vote of confidence.

Concordance 13. Nouns after “China’s” in Xinhua

N	Concordance
1 <title> India fully confident in China's victory over coronavirus outbreak: FM
2 <title> Spotlight: World confident in China's victory over novel coronavirus </title>
3	Roundup: Overseas political parties, organizations express confidence in China's victory over coronavirus </title>
4 <title> Roundup: World grows confident in China's victory against novel coronavirus </tit
5 <title> Feature: German video blogger voices support for China's fight against epidemic </title>
6 <title> Ukrainian composer creates music piece supporting China's fight against coronavirus </title>
7 <title> Senior UN official voices confidence in China's fight against novel coronavirus </title
8 <title> Indonesian policeman sings "Jiayou Wuhan" to cheer on China's fight against COVID-19 </title>
9 <title> Interview: Epidemic unlikely to batter China's economy </title>
10 <title> Coronavirus unlikely to cause long-term setback to China's economy: economists </title>
11 <title> IMF chief "confident" that China's economy "remains resilient" </title> ..
12	Chinese envoy says epidemic will not change positive fundamentals of China's economy </title>
13 <title> Novel coronavirus impact not to reverse growth of China's economy: Chinese state councilor </t
14 <title> Feature: New Zealanders show support for China's battle against COVID-19 </title>
15 <title> Roundup: Foreign party leaders express confidence in China's battle against epidemic </title>

It is this nationalistic stand behind China’s political leadership’s vision coupled with the people’s show of national unity, patriotism, and solidarity that Xinhua is displaying in covering the COVID-19 crisis. Such a position is in line with the discourse functions established by leading CDA theorists (Fairclough, 2003, 2004, 2009; Van Dijk, 2006, 2008, 2009; Wodak, 2009; Wodak & Meyer, 2009).

Compared to Xinhua’s choice of the China+ noun combination, Reuters’ use of the s-genitive with the world China is less affirmative and perhaps indicative of caution. For example “China’s Xi says coronavirus is a ‘devil’ ” (Concordance 14, line 2) does not entail a sense of victory. The same is sounded in (3) “China’s Xi pledges to minimize the impact of virus, and in (4) with North Korea’s Kim offering condolences to China’s Xi. Example (5) is indicative of lack of confidence in managing the virus crisis “Mayor of Chin’s Wuhan says city’s governance ‘not good enough’. The effect of the virus on the Chinese economy is so clearly expressed in (10) ...fears virus to hurt Chinese economy.” A strong signal comes from the U.S. administration as saying (12): “U.S. disappointed with China’s coronavirus response.” Example (9) signals a state of anxiety when “Residents fret as China’s virus exclusion zone widens.” Other countries’ response to evacuating nationals from China are represented in examples 8 and 14 for Turkey and Brazil. And finally, “China’s coronavirus disrupts global container shipping trade” (15) shows the impact of the coronavirus spread on the global economy. Once again, the representation of China in Reuter’s reporting is balanced, objective, and impartial; without reflecting any kind of bias, prejudice, or partisanship.

Concordance 14. Nouns after “China’s” in Reuters

N	Concordance
1	<title> Trump says he spoke to China's Xi, U.S. working closely with China on coronavirus </title>
2	<title> China's Xi says coronavirus is a 'devil' </title>
3	<title> China's Xi pledges to to minimise impact of virus </title>
4	<title> North Korea's Kim offers condolences to China's Xi about virus outbreak: KCNA </title>
5	<title> Mayor of China's Wuhan says city's governance 'not good enough' as virus spreads </title>
6	<title> U.S. citizen died from coronavirus in China's Wuhan </title>
7	<title> Germany calls for calm as evacuees return from China's Wuhan </title>
8	<title> Turkey to evacuate citizens from China's Wuhan over virus outbreak: NTV </title>
9	<title> Residents fret as China's virus exclusion zone widens </title>
10	GLOBAL MARKETS-Stocks, oil tumble on fears virus to hurt China's economy </title>
11	> White House sees minimal impact on U.S. economy from China's coronavirus </title>
12	<title> U.S. disappointed with China's coronavirus response: White House adviser </title>
13	<title> China's coronavirus may help boost U.S. jobs: Ross </title>
14	<title> Brazil draws up plan to evacuate nationals from China's coronavirus epicenter </title>
15	<title> China's coronavirus disrupts global container shipping trade </title>

As Concordance 14 examples show, the word China here links with noun phrases to mark the 'genitive case' where a state of uncertainty, feebleness, concern, and lack of confidence is being expressed. Such discrepancy in concordance between Xinhua's and Reuters' identification of the China + noun combination is most likely to confirm the basic tenets of "self vs. other" in CDA theorizing.

Conclusion and Limitations

The present study has illustrated that the discursive power of discourse analysis is a reality to contend with. The Coronavirus-19 which invaded the globe so suddenly has created a state of es terror, panic, havoc, and repulsive feelings worldwide. As a result, different discourses have been brought to the scene to explicate the intricate relationship between the different domains being affected by the virus. The two major news media hubs to report on the event, Reuters and Xinhua were so most particularly involved in tracking the spread of the virus and its ramifications globally.

The present study has its own limitations as: (1) it only covers the first phase of the COVID-19 outbreak (from January 8, 2020 to February 29, 2020), and (2) it depicts the representation of COVID-19 in two major news outlets through analyzing a corpus of 16,980 English headlines of Reuters and Xinhua. And since WHO has not yet declared the end of the pandemic, more research will be needed to fill gaps and to provide answers to a large number of questions which still surround the mystery COVID-19. In a similar vein, there are growing fears of the emergence of a new coronovirus outbreak in Beijing involving a more contagious strain of the virus than the one that hit Wuhan. To this end, the second phase of our research will provide a more comprehensive coverage and repositioning of COVID-19, pending problems and lessons learned.

From a critical discourse analysis perspective, the representation of the Coronavirus-19 in the news headlines was varied to entail many discourses focusing on key domains top among which is health, economy, society, and psychology. This rigs to light the interdisciplinary nature of critical discourse analysis. The representation of the virus in the news headlines of the two agencies reflected some differences in thematic focus. For example, the detailed analysis of the results showed the wide spectrum of domains and themes that Reuters' news headlines have covered both in the frequency, concordance and collational data. The density in Reuters' reporting was so varied and very high to cover all economic, social, health, aspects worldwide. The reporting was so professional and balanced to present a realistic and objective account on the impact of the virus outbreak on humanity at large irrespective of geography or locale. On the other hand, Xinhua's reporting, which is as professional and reliable as that of Reuters', tended to play down the effect of the coronavirus spread on the Chinese economy, and to highlight the readiness and ability of china to overcome and curb the spread of the disease. More importantly, the density of the news headlines, which focused on maximizing China's role in fighting and conquering the virus, was relatively much smaller than that of Reuters' which was more comprehensive and varied. Xinhua's reporting was -- one way or the other-- geared towards enforcing the 'Us vs. 'Them' dichotomy. Interestingly enough, one of the most crystalizing effects of the Coronavirus-19 crisis is its challenge to the 'positive self' and 'negative other' distinction (Van Dijk, 2006).

The present study has shown that the 'othering' syndrome/phenomenon of 'Us' vs. 'Them' and the 'negative-other' representation which is triggered by a discriminatory condescending look of Western countries to the less developed nations has collapsed. The 'self-positive traits' and 'negative other' fallacy proved fragile when the

health systems of the G-20 countries, with sturdy and resilient economies, collapsed and stood helpless in facing the predatory coronavirus.

In sum, the present study has most forcefully entrenched the vital role of critical discourse analysis (CDA) in analyzing massive corpora to provide authentic analysis of communicative events. The study has most adequately given answers to the research questions of the most frequently discussed topics in the context of coronavirus in the headlines of the two major news agencies and the representation of China in the headlines of the above-mentioned news agencies.

It is noteworthy that the COVID-19 cases and deaths have been soaring steadily with 213 countries being affected (8,552,729 cases) and (455,192 deaths), the present piece of research is not conclusive. As such, the researchers are considering a second phase of data collection which will continue until the virus spread subsides and WHO declares the end of the COVID-19 pandemic.

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